

COMPARATIVE LITERARY STUDIES

Saxibova Dilrabo Ergashevna

English teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13925464>

The comparative historical method is a way of studying and explaining various phenomena, in which, based on the establishment of similarities between these phenomena in form, a conclusion is made about their genetic relationship, i.e. about their common origin. The peculiarity of the comparative historical method used in the study of cultural phenomena is that its starting point is the restoration and comparison of the most ancient elements common to various areas of material culture and knowledge.

Prehistory of comparative historical literary criticism. The first experiments in the field of comparative literary criticism were made in Germany at the end of the 18th century. Comparing multinational cultural and literary traditions, German scholars came to the conclusion about the existence of a single European and world "cultural space". I.G. Herder entered into polemics with Lessing's "Laocoon..." ("Critical Forests..."), showed a deep interest in the folklore of different peoples (collection "Voices of the Peoples in Songs" 1807). It is characterized by the search for the laws of development of human society as a whole - from the lower to the higher levels, the study of the culture of various peoples of the world, including the peoples of Asia and the Slavs ("Ideas for the Philosophy of the History of Mankind"). Herder gives an interpretation of the concepts of "culture", "tradition"; speaks of the dependence of the culture of a people on climate, form of government, religion, etc., asserts historicism in the development of mankind.

Distinctive features of the artistic cultures of the East and West as interpreted by Herder. The problem of continuity of generations and culture in the works of Herder. Contradictions of Herder's concept, its impact on romantic historicism.

Herder draws attention to the commonality of the cultural life of European peoples, and I.-W. Goethe, continuing Herder's ideas, introduces the concept of "world literature" into cultural studies. The idea of the unity of culture, and above all the cultures of the West and the East, which make up world culture in the "West-Eastern Divan". Justification of the connection between cultures by the regularity of the progressive historical process, the essence of which is in the constant interaction of peoples and their cultures, in their mutual influences and mutual borrowings.

Based on the dialectical method and within the framework of its idealistic system, the historicism and aesthetics of G.V.F. Hegel are formed. Geographical and cultural substantiation of the concepts of "East" and "West", determination of the features of spiritual development of Eastern and Western peoples, specificity of Eastern and Western types of aesthetic consciousness. "West" and "East" as two inextricably linked, constantly interacting and essentially opposite spiritual worlds. In studying the history of artistic culture, Hegel relied on the dialectic he created, which allows us to see the opposition of two types of artistic culture as a natural condition of their unity and interaction; the law of negation explains the transition from the symbolic form of art that developed in the ancient East to the higher stages of classical and romantic art, and the latter synthesizes the criteria of Western and Eastern art. Hegel linked symbolic art with the artistic culture of the East, classical art with Greece and Rome, i.e. with Western Europe, and in romantic art he saw a synthesis of the cultures of the East and West with the leading role of the latter. Developing in parallel, the poetry of the East and the poetry of the West, Hegel believes, differ significantly from each other in the uniqueness of content, and special methods of depiction, and specific expressive means. Justification of the idea of the stage-by-stage development of the arts, the historical principle of examining poetry (its themes, characters, conflicts, leading pathos, genres).

Similar constructions of Jean-Paul, F. Schelling and other German aestheticians (division of literature into genres, antithesis of heroic epic and novel, etc.). Hegel's Eurocentrism and his criticism by A.N. Veselovsky.

The source of the comparative-historical method is the aesthetics of romanticism with its characteristic principles of historicism and universality. The affirmation of the individual-authorial artistic consciousness, freedom of creativity, stimulating writers to turn to foreign works created not according to the "rules" of classicism, their creative assimilation (the importance of Shakespeare for Goethe, V. Hugo, Pushkin). The romantic concept of personality, emphasis on the elements of feelings (as opposed to enlightenment rationalism) - and the rehabilitation of the Middle Ages. The growth of national self-awareness: interest in the history of one's people (the emergence of the historical novel: W. Scott; the popularity of ballads based on national history), the collection of folklore (Heidelberg Romantics), the requirement to convey in a work "local color" as well as "the color of the era" ("Preface to the drama "Cromwell" by Hugo). Comparisons of literatures: "naive" and "sentimental" poetry (F. Schiller), new European literatures of the "south" and "north" (J. de

Staël). The emergence of comparative historical linguistics in the bosom of German Romanticism (F. Bopp, R. Rask, J. Grimm, W. Humboldt, etc.); its rapid development and influence on literary criticism and folklore studies; many scholars of the 19th century. were also linguists and literary scholars (J. Grimm, F. I. Buslaev, A. A. Potebnya). Positivism in philosophy (O. Comte, G. Spencer) as a reaction to the speculative, metaphysical nature of the systems of Hegel, Schelling and other German philosophers; the most important principle of positive (i.e., according to Comte, scientific) research is the derivation of "laws" from a repeatedly observed sequence of facts and phenomena. The impossibility of "pure" induction in science; the importance of hypotheses in the creation of scientific directions. The idea of historical development, progress, evolution - in its various versions - as the leading one in the sciences of nature and society throughout almost the entire 19th century. Comparisons of similar phenomena in the folklore and literatures of different peoples, the breadth of the material involved, characteristic of the scientific schools of the 19th century. The genesis of works, images, plots is the main subject of study; the heuristic value of many hypotheses (generally one-sided), their complementarity.

The intensive development of ethnography in the 1830s, including comparative ethnography, gave a new impetus to literary comparative studies.

Identification of a fund of universal, universal themes, motifs, and plots when turning to the works of different peoples, including those at different stages of social development; study of the path of movement of these themes and motifs in time and space, from one national culture (era) to another culture (era). The work of Jacob Grimm, Gaston Paris and other researchers.

The next stage in the development of the comparative historical method, associated with the works of Georg Brandes, Max Koch, G.-M. Posnett. Georg Brandes' idea, expressed in his work "The Main Currents in Literature of the 19th Century", that the genius of one people always needs contact with the geniuses of other peoples, and this gives it strength for development; an appeal to both the mutual connections of national literatures (Max Koch) and their common features associated with the characteristics of social life common to different peoples (G.-M. Posnett).

Proof of polygenesis, the independent emergence of similar forms of life, beliefs, rituals, etc. in societies at the same level of civilization, by representatives of the ethnographic (anthropological) school (E. Tylor, J. Frazer, etc.). "The inhabitants of the lake dwellings of ancient Switzerland can be placed next to the medieval Aztecs..." (Tylor).

The mythological school in folklore studies and literary criticism (J. and V. Grimm, A. Kuhn, M. Müller, F. I. Buslaev, A. N. Afanasyev, O. F. Miller, etc.) and its influence on the formation of the comparative historical method. Rapprochement of folk poetry, language and myth; explanation of similar images and plots in the poetry of Indo-European peoples by their common ancient mythology (proto-myth).

The cultural-historical school (I. Taine, V. Scherer, G. Lanson, G. Brandeis, J. Lewis, A. N. Pypin, N. S. Tikhonravov, etc.) and its influence on the comparative-historical method. A literary work as "a snapshot of the surrounding morals and evidence of a certain state of mind" (Taine); likening a work to a plant growing in a certain soil, and the humanities to natural science. Three different sources ("factors") explaining the features of a work: race, environment, moment ("History of English Literature" by Taine). Strengths of the method, its influence on the sociological, including Marxist, approach to literature (G. V. Plekhanov). At the same time, there is an unclear connection between the "factors" that determine aesthetic phenomena, the leveling of the aesthetic merits of works, since the latter are of interest to the researcher as "monuments" of their time (the works of F.V. Rostopchin for N.S. Tikhonravov), the dissolution of fiction in the history of writing.

Synchronous regular sequence of literary movements, caused by historically similar conditions of development of peoples: Renaissance, Baroque, Classicism, Romanticism, Realism, Naturalism, Modernism, Socialist Realism.

According to V.M. Zhirmunsky, the change of large literary movements and styles is connected both with the change of social ideology and the means of its artistic expression. This is the common basis on which more frequent convergence of ideas, images, plots, genres, and styles is possible. This is a two-sided, dialectical process - the change of literary movements is caused by both internal development and an external push. At the same time, the determining factors for the typology of a literary movement are not external, but internal prerequisites for evolution. Direct influences and borrowings are less common in modern literature than in medieval literature, since the typical and traditional, stable and repetitive are supplanted by an ever greater differentiation of artistic manners. In general, V.M.Zhirmunsky prefers the comparative-typological approach and pays less attention to the problem of contact interactions.

The latter aspect is most thoroughly developed in Russian literary criticism in the works of N.I.Konrad. The concept of "Eastern Renaissance". Definition of

the subject and tasks of comparative studies in the article "Problems of modern comparative literary criticism". Development of the problem of contact interactions in the works of N.I.Konrad. Typology of literary contacts: penetration of a literary text into a foreign cultural environment in its own "guise" - in the original language, the original text when penetrating into a foreign cultural environment does not receive a strictly fixed appearance - each reader creates his own version of the work based on the invariant text; translation, which has become part of the foreign-language culture. The third type of penetration of a foreign-language work, according to N.I.Konrad, is the reproduction in the work of one writer of the content and motives of a work created by a writer of another people. This form was especially widespread in Asia in the Middle Ages, and its illustration can be the literary fate of the plot of Layla and Majnun.

The problem of the literary mediator as a figure in the world literary process that facilitates the implementation of real contacts between cultures. The literary mediator has many faces, and hence the difference in the ways in which one literature can influence another. Types of mediators noted by N.I. Konrad.

The image of the personality of the poet, the "master of thoughts", who attracts the attention of foreigners to the literature and culture of his country not only by his work, but also by his fate (often legendary), his extra-literary activities, as one of the types of mediation. Attention to literary creativity in this case often comes as a consequence of interest in the individual, in the person. A special type of mediation, characteristic of medieval literature, is the activity of masters of oral retelling of foreign-language literature. The third type of mediator, also characteristic of medieval literature, is the wandering singer, musician, buffoon. In addition to those mentioned by N.I. Konrad, the following types of mediators, characteristic primarily of the literature of the New Age, can be distinguished. This is, first of all, the wandering writer, whose contact with a foreign cultural environment leads to the mutual enrichment of both cultures, both literatures. In dramatic periods of the history of modern European countries, situations of mass literary mediation arise, associated with waves of literary emigration. Among literary mediators, publishers occupy a special place.

List of references:

1. Alekseev M.P. Comparative Literary Criticism /M.P. Alekseev. - L. Nauka, Leningrad Branch, 1983. - P.6 - 100.
2. Bushmin A.S. Methodological Issues of Literary Research /A.S. Bushmin. - L. Nauka, 1969. - P.67 - 72.

3. Veselovsky A.N. Historical Poetics /A.N. Veselovsky. - M.: Higher. school, 1989. - P.36 - 41; 310 - 316.
4. Zhirmunsky V.M. Comparative Literary Criticism /V.M. Zhirmunsky. - L.: Nauka, 1979. - P.383-403.
5. Zhirmunsky V.M. Epic creativity of the Slavic peoples and problems of comparative study of the epic / V.M.Zhirmunsky // Studies in Slavic literary criticism and folklore studies. - M.: Publishing house of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1960. - P. 252-254.
6. Kalacheva S. Comparativism / S.Kalacheva // Dictionary of literary terms. - M., 1974. - P.149-152.
7. Konrad N.I. West and East: articles / N.I.Konrad. - M.: Science, Chief editor of Eastern Literature, 1972. - P.315-329.

